

16S NMDS

PREAK SDEI LEAVES

ROVIENG LEAVES

PREAK SDEI RHIZOSPHERE

ROVIENG RHIZOSPHERE

PREAK SDEI ROOT

ROVIENG ROOT

18S NMDS

PREAK SDEI RHIZOSPHERE

ROVIENG RHIZOSPHERE

PREAK SDEI ROOT

ROVIENG ROOT

